

ISic3724

I.Sicily inscription 3724

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra del Monte Rosa)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Found in 1952 in excavation of trench XI (pro. Cincotta-Giuffre, via Diana, reuse as cover of t.151)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 977

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334813

1. Κ(οίντου) □ Λουτατίου

2. Δώρου.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334813

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1381.113bis

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 705

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3724. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4389053>